

A STUDY ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND ADJUSTMENT OF SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study is to find out the Adjustment and Academic Achievement of Visual Impaired school students in Sikkim. The sample of the study comprised of 100 Visual impaired school students. The methodology used for the study was Descriptive survey method. Results indicated that majority of the Visual Impaired school students are extremely maladjusted and have a low academic achievement and that there is no significant difference in the home, social, emotional and school adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender.

Keywords: Adjustment, Academic Achievement, Inclusive Education, Visually Impaired School Students

INTRODUCTION

Adjustment as the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs (Shaffer, as cited in Mangal, 2010). According to Symonds (1943), "a person is said to be adjusted when he is relatively happy, efficient and has some degree of social feeling. In simple words adjustment is all inclusive term meaning relationship between an individual and his environment through which his needs are satisfied in accordance with social demands." (Sharma, 2008)

Inclusive Education is a new approach towards educating the children with disability and learning difficulties with that of normal ones within the same roof. Inclusive Education is one of the most effective ways in which to promote an inclusive and tolerant society (Singh, 2016). The differently abled students face many problems in their adequate adjustment on account of their deformity. The differently abled student is unable to participate in desirable normal activities and this incapability leads to feeling of inferiority and self-

pity hence the students may develop adjustment problems with these feelings (Bala and Rao, 2007).

Visual impairment is a condition in which a student's vision is deficient to such a degree that it significantly affects his school functioning. Another description may also be used to classify an individual as Visual impairment is a condition in which a student's vision is deficient to such a degree that it significantly affects his school functioning. Another description may also be used to classify an individual as Visual impairment is a condition in which a student's vision is deficient to such a degree that it significantly affects his school functioning. Another description may also be used to classify an individual as Visual impairment is a condition in which a student's vision is deficient to such a degree that it significantly affects his school functioning. Another description may also be used to classify an individual as blind. If the visual field is severely limited, that person may be considered blind even if visual acuity is better than 20/200. This visual field limitation is often called tunnel vision. If the visual field is not greater than 20 degrees in width, the

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individual can still be classified as being blind even though visual acuity is not within typical range of the vision in his better eye (after correction) is less than 20/70 but better than 20/200. Such children need special equipment's and are often taught in special classes or resource rooms that provide special methods and materials. In many cases they can be educated in a regular class if special material and equipment are provided. A person is defined as 'Blind' if his vision or visual acuity (after correction) is 20/200 in his better eye. This visual acuity is in general inadequate for education through the eyes, and special techniques have been devised to make possible education through tactual and auditory channels (Panda, 1997)

Pothuraj and Yashoda (2014) reported that visually impaired students had good adjustment at school. Rajkonwar, Dutta and Soni (2015) there was no difference in the overall adjustment of visual impaired students with regard to gender and that there was no difference in the academic achievement of visually impaired students with regard to gender.

Jha (2018) disabled student's had low academic achievement, their participation in academics was low but their absence was high. Pandey (2018) indicated that there was a significant difference in the adjustment of the visually impaired students attending the special and the integrated schools. Dhara and Barman (2020) revealed that there is no significant difference in the adjustment of differently abled students with regard to the variable of gender.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To study the adjustment and Academic Achievement of Visual Impaired school students in Sikkim.
2. To find out the difference in the Home adjustment of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.
3. To find out the difference in the Social adjustment of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.

4. To find out the difference in the Emotional adjustment of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.
5. To find out the difference in the School adjustment of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.
6. To find out the difference in the Academic achievement of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.

HYPOTHESES

- H0₁ There is no significant difference in the Home adjustment of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.
- H0₂ There is no significant difference in the Social adjustment of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.
- H0₃ There is no significant difference in the Emotional adjustment of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.
- H0₄ There is no significant difference in the School adjustment of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.
- H0₅ There is no significant difference in the Academic Achievement of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.

METHODOLOGY

In the present study descriptive survey method was used. The sample for the study comprised of 100 Visual Impaired students studying in various schools of Sikkim. Out of which 58 were female students and 42 were male students. The technique used to collect sample was Stratified random sampling technique. The tool used for the study was HOSOCES Adjustment Inventory developed by N.A Nadeem in the year 2002. The statistical techniques used for the study comprised of percentage, mean, standard deviation and t-test.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Objective 1: To study the adjustment of Visual Impaired school students in Sikkim.

Table 1 : Overall adjustment of Visual Impaired school students in Sikkim

Level of Adjustment	Score group	Visual Impaired (N=100)	
		f	%
Extremely Adjusted	0 – 4	0	0%
Highly Adjusted	5 – 14	2	2%
Average/Well Adjusted	15 – 23	14	14%
Poorly Adjusted	24 – 33	29	29%
Extremely Maladjusted	34 and above	55	55%

Table 1 shows the overall adjustment of Visual Impaired school students in Sikkim. Majority of the Visual Impaired students i.e. 55% fall under the Extremely Maladjusted category. While 29% of the Visual Impaired school students fall under the Poorly Adjusted category. 14% of the Visual Impaired school students fall under the Average Adjustment category.

Further it may be observed that the number Visual Impaired school students under the Extremely Adjusted category is found to be nil.

Objective 1: To study the adjustment of Visual Impaired school students in Sikkim.

Table 2 : Academic achievement of Visual Impaired school students in Sikkim

Classification	Score group	Visual Impaired (N=100)	
		f	%
Very High Achievers	Above 80%	0	0%
High Achievers	60% - 79%	2	2%
Average Achievers	45% - 59%	15	15%
Low Achievers	31% - 44%	31	31%
Very Low Achievers	30 & below	52	52%

Table 2 shows the Academic achievement of Visual Impaired school students in Sikkim. Majority of the Visual Impaired students i.e. 52% are found to be very low achievers. While 31% of the Visual Impaired school students fall under the Low achievers category. 15% of the Visual Impaired school students fall under the Average achievers category. Further it may be observed that only 2% of the Visual impaired students fall under the High achievers category and the number

Visual Impaired school students under the Very high achievers category is found to be nil.

Objective 2: To find out the difference in the Home adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender.

H₀ There is no significant difference in the Home adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender.

Table 3: Home Adjustment of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.					
(df = 98) (Table value at 0.05 level = 1.98)					
Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Male	42	6.16	2.70	0.016	Not Significant at 0.05 level
Female	58	8.05	4.53		

It is evident from Table 3 that there is no significant difference in the home adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

Objective 3: To find out the difference in the Social adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender

H0₂ There is no significant difference in the Social adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender

Table 4: Social Adjustment of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.					
(df = 98) (Table value at 0.05 level = 1.98)					
Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Male	42	12.90	4.72	0.0090	Not Significant at 0.05 level
Female	58	10.72	3.46		

It is evident from Table 4 that there is no significant difference in the social adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

Objective 4: To find out the difference in the Emotional adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender.

H0₃ There is no significant difference in the Emotional adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender.

Table 5: Emotional Adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender

(df = 98) (Table value at 0.05 level = 1.98)

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Male	42	11.42	4.24	0.082	Not significant at 0.05 level
Female	58	10.10	3.78		

It is evident from Table 5 that there is no significant difference in the emotional adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

Objective 5: To find out the difference in the School adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender.

H0₄ There is no significant difference in the School adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender.

Table 6: School Adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender					
(df = 98) (Table value at 0.05 level = 1.98)					
Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Male	42	10.47	5.37	0.63	Not significant at 0.05 level
Female	58	9.96	5.27		

It is evident from Table 6 that there is no significant difference in the school adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

Objective 6: To find out the difference in the Academic achievement of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.

H0₅ There is no significant difference in the Academic achievement of Visual impaired school students with regard to gender.

Table 7: Academic achievement of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender					
(df = 98) (Table value at 0.05 level = 1.98)					
Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Male	42	43.02	9.87	1.06	Not significant at 0.05 level
Female	58	23.68	4.99		

It is evident from Table 7 that there is no significant difference in the Academic achievement of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

of Rajkonwar, Dutta and Soni (2015) who revealed that there was no difference in the overall adjustment of Visual impaired students on the basis of gender. This could be because both the male and the female Visually Impaired students receive similar facilities and face similar issues of adjustment in school and home in Sikkim. As Sikkim gender biases are not common in the state of Sikkim. The study also revealed that there is no significant difference in the Academic achievement of Visual impaired students with regard to gender.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The study found that majority of the Visual Impaired school students are extremely maladjusted and have a low Academic achievement. This finding differs with the finding of Pothuraj and Yashoda (2014) who reported that visually impaired students had good adjustment at school. The probable reason may be due to lack of proper awareness regarding Inclusive Education among the school staff, inaccessible infrastructure, unavailability of well trained resource teachers, absence of resource rooms and appropriate instructional materials for the Visual Impaired school students.

CONCLUSION

Adjustment is a continuous process by which a person varies his behaviour to produce a more harmonious relationship between himself and his environment. An adjusted child is one who attacks problems directly, accepts and tolerates normal amount of frustration, acts rationally, makes sincere efforts to reach his goal, enjoys company of others, is cheerful and energetic and possesses an optimistic view of life and things around him (Bala and Rao, 2007). On account of their disability the students with Visual Impairment could encounter difficulties adjusting in an Inclusive setup. Hence it is very important for the policy makers,

The study also found that there is no significant difference in the home, social, emotional and school adjustment of Visual Impaired school students with regard to gender. This finding is in line with the finding

teachers and people working in the field of education provide appropriate infrastructure, instructional materials, ambience to gratify the social, psychological and educational needs of the Visual Impaired students.

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